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The Utilization of Ipil-Ipil (*Leucaena leucocephala*) Charcoal and Used Engine Oil as Alternative Ink for Whiteboard Markers

John Lloyd P. Alarcon, Joey Henlee J. Baldevarona, Patrisha Lei C. Clotario, Ma. Jessa Dianne B. Morala, Kairha Kirsten B. Singcay

Senior High School Department, Paramount School of Arts, Languages, Management, and Sciences, Incorporated, Bagontaas, Valencia City, Bukidnon, Philippines, 8709.

Corresponding Author: John Lloyd P. Alarcon

Email of the Corresponding Author: alarcon.johnlloydpalmes@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study aims to assess the potential of Ipil-Ipil (*Leucaena leucocephala*) charcoal and used engine oil as an alternative ink for whiteboard markers. This quantitative study used experimental research as its design and used descriptive statistics in data analysis. The study results revealed that the respondents accepted the color intensity, consistency, and scent supported by the t-test result, which shows a significant difference between the acceptability of the alternative and commercialized ink. This study contributes to developing sustainable and effective writing tools by analyzing and offering environmentally friendly choices for diverse situations.

Keywords: alternative ink, sustainability, charcoal product, whiteboard markers

INTRODUCTION

Ink is a suspension of tiny colored or uncolored particles, called pigments, in a liquid, typically water or oil. It is made up of four main ingredients: pigments, which provide the color; binders, which hold the pigments together; solvents, which help the ink flow; and additives, which improve other properties of the ink, such as drying time or resistance to fading (Oko-Udu, 2014). Inks often contain harmful ingredients like solvents derived from non-renewable sources, posing risks to both people and the environment. These risks can include headaches, skin irritation, and even nervous system damage, potentially caused by components like p-anisidine (Mohd Basri, Liew Min Ren, Talib, Zakaria, & Kamarudin, 2021).

Eco-friendly alternatives are being explored to avoid the harmful effects of commercial whiteboard marker ink materials. This study examined the potential of Ipil-ipil (*Leucaena leucocephala*) charcoal and used engine oil as an alternative to whiteboard marker ink. The goal is to contribute to developing sustainable and effective writing tools by analyzing and offering environmentally friendly choices for diverse situations.

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Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the potential of Ipil-Ipil (*Leucaena leucocephala*) and used engine oil as an effective alternative ink for whiteboard markers. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Evaluate the innovative ink formulation from *Leucaena leucocephala* charcoal and commercial whiteboard ink performance in terms of:
 - a. color intensity
 - b. consistency
 - c. scent
2. Identify the acceptability rate between substitute ink and commercialized ink

Research Paradigm

Figure 1: The relationship between independent and dependent variables

Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference between the acceptability rate of alternative and commercialized ink.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This paper is a quantitative study that utilized an experimental research design to assess the effectiveness of Ipil-ipil (*Leucaena leucocephala*) charcoal and used engine oil as alternative ink for whiteboard markers.

Participants of the Study

The product of this study was tested by the 20 teachers of the Paramount School of Arts, Languages, Management, and Sciences, Incorporated. The teachers used the product during their classes for about one week, and then they were given a survey questionnaire to assess the performance of the alternative ink.

Research Instrument

To assess the acceptability rate of the alternative ink, this research adapted the questionnaire used by Barradema (2022) in evaluating the respondents' acceptability rate of innovative and commercialized ink in his study entitled, *The Use*

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of Charcoal and Isopropyl Alcohol as Alternative Ink for Whiteboard Markers: A Comparative Analysis between the Innovation and Commercialized Ink.

The instrument used the Likert Scale (see Table 1) to measure the data from the participants. The respondents are asked to indicate their level of agreement with a given statement using an ordinal scale.

Table 1: Scaling Matrix

Scale	Interval	Descriptive Rating
4	3.26-4.00	Very Acceptable
3	2.51-3.25	Acceptable
2	1.76-2.50	Quite Acceptable
1	1.00-1.75	Not Acceptable

Data Analysis Method

The data was taken from the respondents using descriptive statistics and a t-test (for comparison of substitute and commercialized ink) using the IBM SPSS Statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Acceptability Rates of the Ipil-Ipil (*Leucaena leucocephala*) Charcoal and Used Engine Oil as Alternative Ink for Whiteboard Marker

Color Intensity of the Alternative Ink

Table 2: Result of the Color Intensity Assessment

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
The ink creates an appealing deep black color to the eyes.	3.37	Very Acceptable
The intensity of the ink has satisfied me.	3.20	Acceptable
The intensity of the ink does not produce wet marks.	3.18	Acceptable
The ink is visible from a distance.	2.90	Acceptable
The ink sustains its intensity after a while	2.79	Acceptable
Overall Mean	3.06	Acceptable

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Table 2 shows the results of the respondents' evaluation using the alternative whiteboard marker ink in terms of color intensity. The results revealed an overall mean of 3.06 which is acceptable in the following indicators, namely: "The ink creates an appealing deep black color to the eyes" (3.27); "The intensity of the ink has satisfied me", (3.20); "The intensity of the ink does not produce wet marks", (3.18); "The ink is visible from a distance", (2.90); and "The ink sustains its intensity after a while", (2.79). It implies that the respondents find the color intensity satisfying and acceptable as an alternative to commercial whiteboard ink.

In the study of Cruto (2019), the charcoal ink was rated "very good" in terms of color. The charcoal ink exhibited a deep, rich black color with minimal grey, blue, or brown undertones, resulting in a highly neutral and aesthetically pleasing hue. The study by Mohd Basri et al. (2021) tested the dry mangosteen leaves' viscosity, color lightness, and drying properties. The result revealed the lightness of the color of the ink, which is very acceptable to use.

Consistency of the Alternative Ink

Table 3 reveals the assessment results for consistency of the alternative ink. It indicates an overall mean of 3.22, which mean "acceptable" from the following indicators: "The ink can be erased easily", (3.34); "The ink is not messy", (3.29); "The ink does not fade easily", (3.25); "The ink easily dries when used", (3.17); and "The viscosity of the ink has satisfied me", (3.06). This implies that the alternative ink sustains its qualities, such as viscosity, and can be easily erased, revealing the acceptability of the alternative ink in terms of consistency.

Table 3: Result of the Consistency Assessment

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
The ink can be erased easily	3.34	Very Acceptable
The ink is not messy.	3.29	Very Acceptable
The ink does not fade easily	3.25	Acceptable
The ink easily dries when used.	3.17	Acceptable
The viscosity of the ink has satisfied me	3.06	Acceptable
Overall Mean	3.22	Acceptable

Barrameda (2022) reveals that in terms of consistency, charcoal ink has a reasonable acceptability rate. The particles of charcoal explain this as the main

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reason the innovative ink fades quickly. Hence, it is essential to pulverize smoothly the charcoal for the creative ink to sustain its black color when used.

Scent of the Alternative Ink

Table 4 shows the evaluation results of the scent of the alternative ink. It reveals an overall score of 3.35 which means "Very Acceptable" from the following indicators: "The ink produces a pleasant smell", (3.54); "The ink has a distinctive smell", (3.37); "The smell of the ink does not make me dizzy", (3.33); "The smell of the ink has no disturbing effect to the user", (3.26); and "The ink has an overall tolerable smell", (3.24). This implies that the scent of the alternative ink manifests a good smell that appears tolerable to the respondents. Using fewer chemicals decreases the strong scent of a substance.

Table 4: Result of the Scent Assessment

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
The ink produces a pleasant smell	3.54	Very Acceptable
The ink has a distinctive smell	3.37	Very Acceptable
The smell of the ink does not make me dizzy	3.33	Very Acceptable
The smell of the ink has no disturbing effect to the user.	3.26	Very Acceptable
The ink has an overall tolerable smell.	3.24	Acceptable
Overall Mean	3.35	Very Acceptable

Mohan and Dhurai's (2020) study revealed that using charcoal results in the formation of anti-odor properties. Charcoal has an incredibly high internal surface area due to its numerous microscopic pores. These pores act like tiny magnets, trapping odor molecules as they come into contact with the charcoal. Rice and Koziel (2015) suggested that a decrease in chemical concentration causes a reduction in the odor of the substance.

Analysis on the Significant Difference between the Alternative Ink and Commercial Ink

Table 6 below shows the statistical comparison of the alternative and commercial ink using a t-test. The test revealed significant differences at $p < 0.05$ between alternative and commercial ink in all three qualities: color intensity, consistency, and

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scent. Thus, the null hypothesis of this study is rejected. This implies that the respondents accept the alternative ink as a better product than the commercial ink.

Table 6: Statistical comparison of alternative and commercial ink using t-test

Qualities	Alternative Ink	Commercial Ink	t-value	p-value	Significance	Decision
Color Intensity	3.06	2.54	-4.33	0.00619	Significant	Reject H ₀
Consistency	3.22	2.80	-8.03	0.00065	Significant	Reject H ₀
Scent	3.35	3.16	-3.38	0.01389	Significant	Reject H ₀

* $p < 0.05$

The study of Barrameda (2022) revealed that the subjects highly accepted the innovation compared to commercialized whiteboard ink. This further testifies to the truthfulness of the previous assumption on the effectiveness of the innovation over the commercialized ink concerning the respondents' perceptions.

Conclusion

Based on the result, the acceptability of the alternative ink is higher than the commercial ink in terms of color intensity, consistency, and scent. Regarding color intensity, consistency, and scent, the alternative has an average respondent acceptance rate. It is further supported by the t-test result, in which a significant difference exists between alternative ink and commercialized ink. This implies that the respondents accept the alternative ink; therefore, the Ipil-Ipil (*Lucaena leucocephala*) charcoal and used engine oil can be used as substitute ink for commercialized ink for whiteboard makers.

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